

Ameratunga et al. fail to refute Autoimmune/autoinflammatory syndrome induced by adjuvants (ASIA)

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Introduction

Ameratunga et al (1). attempt to refute Autoimmune/autoinflammatory syndrome induced by adjuvants (ASIA).

Ameratunga et al. seem to ignore the fundamental mechanism involved in the induction of autoimmunity.

Two factors are needed to induce autoimmunity.

- a) Immune system exposure to an antigen that exhibits molecular mimicry to a self antigen.
- b) Simultaneous innate immune system activation either by an immunological adjuvant or an infection (including live virus vaccine).

Point by point analysis

Referring to ASIA, Ameratunga et al. write: “The criterion does not specify which vaccines or infections are triggers for the disorder”

All vaccines contain numerous non-target proteins (animal, food, bacterial, viral, fungal) with molecular mimicry to human self-antigens (2). Most vaccines contain an adjuvant or live virus that supply the required innate immune system activation. Therefore most vaccines can cause autoimmunity. Infections rarely result in autoimmunity due to the activation of natural protections (fail-safe mechanisms) against autoimmunity, evolved over millions of years (3).

Ameratunga et al. write: “This criterion could include the entire community because everyone has had either a vaccine or an infection.”

Yes, and therefore as expected, common diseases such as autism (4), heart disease, stroke, obesity, diabetes, all have an autoimmune basis (5). And these diseases are prevalent in highly vaccinated populations. During infections, natural fail-safe mechanisms against autoimmunity are active. Not so during immune response to vaccines (6,7).

Ameratunga et al. write: “A recent study suggested that the lag time for ASIA can vary from 2 days to 23 years. Such a large variation in lead time makes it very difficult to undertake randomized studies to determine causality”

You cannot modify disease processes to make them convenient for inappropriate study approaches! Autoimmune diseases can take decades to manifest themselves as they may slowly destroy organs (e.g islet cell destruction in type 1 diabetes).

The appropriate approach is bioinformatics analysis and autoimmune serology as suggested by Wraith et al (3). and Verdier (8), during vaccine clinical trials to **avoid** causing these diseases in the first place.

Tools such as CHOPPI are used to study the same problem of host protein contamination related autoimmunity risk in biologics (9).

Ameratunga et al. write: “given the level of exposure to aluminum in allergen desensitization preparations, we would expect a rapid onset of IBS in patients undergoing immunotherapy.”

Ameratunga et al. make the incorrect assumption that the adjuvant by itself causes IBS. No. IBS causation will depend on the specific antigen adsorbed on the surface of the adjuvant particles. They have to show that antigens involved in immunotherapy have strong molecular mimicry to IBS related self antigens. Otherwise, there is no reason to expect rapid onset of IBS in patients undergoing immunotherapy.

Adjuvant “power” and T cell receptor binding affinity

In many models of autoimmunity such as Experimental Autoimmune Encephalomyelitis (EAE), Complete Freund Adjuvant (CFA) is used along with CNS extract or proteins. Since these proteins are self proteins with 100% molecular mimicry, the immune system will strongly resist induction of autoimmunity. The T cells that recognize these epitopes with high affinity would have been negatively selected in the thymus. So there are few such T cells in the periphery. The immune system has strong tolerance for self proteins. For these reasons a “powerful” adjuvant such as CFA is needed to abrogate tolerance and produce autoimmunity.

With vaccines, we have animal proteins being injected. Animal proteins do not have 100% molecular mimicry to human self proteins. There are numerous regions in the protein sequence where there are single amino acid residue differences. For this reason, animal proteins are ideally suited for recognition by low affinity self reactive (LASR) T cells. LASR T cells are positively selected in the thymus and enter the periphery. They recognize epitopes that differ from self epitopes by a single amino acid residue, with high affinity. But have low affinity to self proteins but enough to be functional (10). LASR T cells are plentiful as they have a role in cancer defense. Activation of these T cells is not as difficult as the activation of high affinity self reactive T cells. Therefore, LASR T cells can be activated with less “powerful” adjuvants such as aluminum salts, to produce autoimmunity, in the presence of animal proteins.

More point by point analysis

Ameratunga et al. write: “In a prospective clinical trial, there was no increase in exacerbations in a cohort of patients with systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) (n = 28) given the hepatitis B vaccine.”

All Hepatitis B vaccines are not created equal. Engerix B (11) has 500% yeast protein content as compared to the Recombivax HB (12) vaccine. In the cited study (13), the Euvax B vaccine was used and its yeast content is undocumented. Euvax B and Engerix B used aluminum hydroxide, while Recombivax uses amorphous aluminum hydroxyphosphate sulfate (AAHS). The problem with such unregulated antigens is of course the inability to replicate studies. Other studies have shown yeast containing aluminum adjuvanted vaccines can cause SLE (14).

Further, if the disease is in a “saturated” state, there may be no exacerbation.

Ameratunga et al. write: “Similarly, the link between hepa-titis B vaccine and multiple sclerosis has been discounted”

“Previous studies have also refuted the Haemophilus influenzae type B vaccine as a cause of diabetes”

As stated before, with uncontrolled antigens in vaccines, these studies **cannot** refute anything. We need to know the residual protein content for all non-target antigens in the vaccine before any conclusion can be drawn.

What is the antigen in Hepatitis B vaccine linked to multiple sclerosis? If there are no antigens with strong molecular mimicry, then the investigation is pointless. Haemophilus influenzae type B residual proteins do have molecular mimicry to some diabetes related epitopes (2). However, diabetes can be caused by numerous vaccines. Without proper controls, type II errors are common.

Ameratunga et al. write: “The strongest argument against the existence of ASIA caused by aluminum-containing vaccine adjuvants is the decreased incidence of autoimmune disease in patients receiving aluminum-containing allergen-specific IT.”

No. IT likely has few antigens with molecular mimicry to self antigens and is therefore an inappropriate comparison to animal protein containing vaccines. So the “strongest argument” is easily dismantled.

Alutard, the immunotherapy agent used in the above IT study (15), contains aluminum hydroxide. So it cannot be compared to AAHS containing vaccines either.

Ameratunga et al. write: “ASIA because autoimmunity is likely to be a rare event”

As stated before, autoimmunity is very common. It is just that common ailments have not been classified as autoimmune disorders even though they are.

Ameratunga et al. write: “In our view, and that of others, the association between vaccination and autoimmunity is likely to be spurious, most likely the result of random events or confounding rather than causality”

Absolutely not true. Forget association. There is plenty of vastly superior mechanistic evidence demonstrating causality. Vaccines cause numerous autoimmune disorders as detailed above.

Immunotherapy is disease state switching – pretending to be a cure

Aeroallergen allergy is an iatrogenic disease induced by aeroallergen containing vaccines (16). IT is not a cure. It merely induces the next iatrogenic disease in the cascade of iatrogenic diseases. IT desensitizes by the induction of allergen specific IgG4 (17–20). The result is the explosion of IgG4 related diseases in the last decade, including diseases such as eosinophilic esophagitis (EoE) (21).

Conclusion

The authors have failed to refute ASIA. Their “strongest” argument is fundamentally flawed. Vaccines definitely cause numerous autoimmune disorders. There is plenty of strong mechanistic evidence (2). The US Institute of Medicine has concluded that in an overwhelming 93% of the cases, mechanistic

studies provided convincing evidence linking vaccines to adverse events and epidemiological studies fail to do so (22). Therefore reliance must be on mechanistic evidence not epidemiological.

To make vaccines safe, all non-target proteins must be immediately removed using processes such as affinity chromatography (23).

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